

The Deictics-Contextualization Praxis in Fictional Communication Acts

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Abstract

Communication acts do not take place in a vacuum; they take place in a context. Interlocutors connect linguistic codes used in a communication event to one level of context or the other. In particular, there are certain frequently occurring words and expressions that require contextualization without which meaning cannot be made of them. Such words and expressions, referred to as deictics, are defined within the domain of pragmatics as being directly connected to the context in which they occur. This paper studies the occurrence of these kinds of expressions and how when they do occur, participants in conversations connect them to context in order to make meaning out of them. The data for the study are drawn from the communication acts of the characters in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*, a fictional text. Conversations among the characters are analysed to establish the nature and regularity of occurrence of these expressions. It is concluded that the propensity of encoders to use deictic expressions and the ability of decoders to situate them and extrapolate their meanings reflect the constancy of contextualization in human communication events. The evidence of their frequency in the fictional world is representative of their preponderance in real life.

Key words: Deictics, Context, Contextualization, Communication, Meaning, Pragmatics

Résumé

Les actes de la communication n'ont pas lieu dans le vide; ils se déroulent dans un contexte. Les interlocuteurs relient les codes linguistiques utilisés dans une situation de communication à un autre niveau ou contexte. En particulier, certains mots et expressions fréquemment utilisés nécessitent la prise en compte du contexte situationnel sans lequel, aucun sens ne peut être tiré. Ces mots et expressions, appelés déictiques, sont définis dans le domaine de la pragmatique, comme étant directement liés au contexte dans lequel ils se produisent. Cet article étudie l'emploi de ces types d'expressions et comment, les participants aux conversations les relient au contexte lorsqu'elles se produisent afin de leur donner un sens. Les données de cette étude sont tirées des actes de communication des personnages de *Hibiscus pourpre* de Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, un texte fictif. Les conversations entre les personnages sont analysées pour établir la nature et la régularité de l'emploi de ces expressions. Nous concluons que la tendance des codeurs à utiliser les expressions déictiques et la capacité des décodeurs à les situer et à en extrapoler des significations, reflètent la constance du contexte dans les situations de communication humaine. La preuve de leur fréquence dans le monde fictif est représentative de leur prépondérance dans la vie réelle.

Mots-clés: Déictique, contexte, situation contextuelle, communication, sens, pragmatique

Introduction

Human beings use the languages they acquire/learn spontaneously and effortlessly when they have to. They come to use the languages without giving a thought to the complexities of the sound systems, word structures, sentence structures and meaning systems of the languages or to their (the users') own rationality, pragmatism and creativity in using them. They do not contemplate how every time they construct novel sentences or comprehend the novel sentences that they hear, they draw from a continuum of inputs at various levels of context and schemata of knowledge. They do not think how perceptive or ingenious or creative they are in being able to generate new sentences and utterances and to make meaning of the new ones they hear in the language. Akmajian and others (2001: p. 149) observe that:

All of us, as native speakers of a language, are able to produce and comprehend an unlimited number of phrases and sentences of that language, many of which we have never heard or produced before. Speakers of a language are enormously creative in their production of novel sentences. [And] we are not just uttering the same sentences over and over again.

A user of a language just becomes a 'master' of the language, "doing things with words" in it (Austin, 1975), constructing fresh sentences of different patterns and lengths and comprehending them without any special effort or thought. It has been observed how even with the lowest general learning aptitudes, people easily acquire and use languages whether it is their first or second language (Cohen and Dornyei, 2002). Fromkin and Rodman (1983: p. 325) note that:

Before they can add 2+2, children are conjoining sentences, asking questions, selecting appropriate pronouns, negating sentences, using syntactic, phonological, morphological and semantic rules. Yet they are not taught language as they are taught arithmetic.

The observation above may be said to be most applicable to the acquisition and use of a first language but it could apply to the learning and use of a second or even a third language depending on the circumstances the person is exposed to. Cohen and Dornyei (2002: p. 172) assert that "the majority of people are able to achieve at least a working knowledge of an L2 regardless of their aptitude ..." It is natural for them to know and use a language or two or more in spite of their inability to perform other tasks that require some degree of intelligence such as to work out sums or rationalize in challenging circumstances. They just display their abilities in language use as if it were such a simple task; they pay no attention to or are unaware of the 'profound knowledge' that is required and drawn from in order to 'carry out the simplest conversation' (Fromkin and Rodman, 1983: p.4) because of the presumption of the ordinariness of the task.

Contrary to this common thinking, studies have revealed the scientific and complex nature of language itself and the profundity of the processes and the inputs in language use. It is established that much actually goes into the use of language. The thinking, constructing,

expressing, comprehending, interpreting, the extrapolation, most of which take place intuitively and simultaneously, that speakers and listeners alike engage in while they use language are all complex tasks. Psychological, neurological and sociological inputs go into the exercise as the human mind and the brain process and/or receive volumes of data/information as well as explore various levels of knowledge to make and share meaning in each communication event. Akmajian and others (2001: 363) note that:

As common and effortless as it is to talk, using language successfully is a very complex enterprise, as anyone knows who has tried as an adult to master a second language. Moreover, much goes into using a language besides knowing it and being able to produce and recognize sentences in it.

Among other instances, the deployment and interpretation of deictics in conversations are evidential instances of how the otherwise complex tasks in language use are discharged with ease because of various levels of contextualization explored by language users. When deictics occur, so often as they do in conversations, interactants necessarily but easily connect them to the context of use to understand their meanings or referents.

The knowledge that the human mind refers to and draws from so quickly and so easily is both language-based and context-based. The language-based data avail the users of the words, phrases and sentences from which they make choices including those of deictic expressions and patterns of construction and to interpret them while the context-based data enable them to connect the words and the patterns of construction to non-linguistic factors such as the participants, tenor, beliefs, shared knowledge, occasion, etc thereby establishing meanings of expressions and helping to achieve effective communication. So, linguistic and non-linguistic knowledge interact for the achievement of communication. Without that interaction, the meaning of an expression or a word may remain abstract or ambiguous and language use would not be seen to have achieved its purpose – exchanging mutually understandable information.

The inextricable connection between language and context in assigning meaning is most evident in the use of deictics. Non-linguistic factors cannot be ignored in the effective interpretation of language, these expressions in particular, since knowledge is often drawn from outside linguistic codes themselves to facilitate understanding. According to Kress and Hodge (1979: p. 13), “... without immediate and direct relations to the social context, the forms and functions of language are not fully explicable”. Kress and Hodge’s assertion extends Leckie-Tarry’s (1995: p. 29) claim that “for communication to occur, the speaker/writer must assume that the addressee possesses similar knowledge [sic] at each contextual level, organized by similar schematic systems to allow interpretation of meaning”. In particular, there are these words and expressions in every language which require users to connect to the context of their use without which meaning will be lost. When deictics are used, interlocutors must have recourse to certain points (time, place, person) of their origin which determine their interpretation or meaning.

The meaning and contextualization of deictics

Deictics also called deixis or deictic expressions are words and expressions whose meanings are wholly dependent upon the physical context in which they are used. They depend for their meanings on the speakers/hearers, place, time and occasion of their use. Pronouns such as 'I', 'he', 'she', 'we', 'them', 'this', 'you' etc, adverbials such as 'here', 'there', 'now', 'then', 'next', 'yesterday', 'tomorrow', 'in the house', 'at the back' etc and demonstratives such as 'this', 'that', 'these' and 'those' are examples of expressions with meanings which are not stable or cannot be determined unless they are linked to their users and time and place of use. This is because the referents of such expressions are not fixed; they differ according to context or use. The personal pronoun 'He' for instance, can refer to Abang or John or Hassan or Bayo at various times; so also the adverbial 'there' can mean 'at home', 'in the bag', 'in the office' etc at various times and a hearer must share a speaker's knowledge to give meaning to those expressions on hearing them. McGregor (2009: p. 145) observes that "The reference of these items varies with each context in which they are used". According to Lyons (2002: p. 293) deixis "...depends crucially upon the time and place of utterance and upon the speaker's (more precisely, the locutionary agent's) and the addressee's roles in the utterance-act itself". Fromkin and Rodman (1983: p. 190) view deixis as an aspect of pragmatics and observe that: "In all languages, there are many words and expressions whose references rely entirely on the circumstances of the utterance and can only be understood if one knows these circumstances. [Such] words and expressions are deictics".

Similarly, Levinson (1983: p. 54) points out that: "The single most obvious way in which the relationship between language and context is reflected in the structures of languages themselves, is through the phenomenon of deixis" and that "deixis belongs within the domain of pragmatics because it directly concerns the relationship between the structures of language and the contexts in which they are used" (1983: p. 55). Yule (2003: pp.129-130) lists some words which occur in deictic expressions, saying that they are impossible to interpret out of context. He states:

There are some words in the language that cannot be interpreted at all unless the physical context, especially the physical context of the speaker is known. These are words like *here, there, this, that, now, then, yesterday* as well as pronouns such as *I, you, him, her, them*. Some sentences of English are virtually impossible to understand if we don't know who is speaking, about whom, where and when.

We add that personal names (Mary, Njagu, Berto, Fiona, Ibrahim etc) are also in the class of deictics because the same names are borne by different people in different places at different times and so, they have no static or fixed referents.

With deictics not referring to particular entities or not standing for the same persons or things on all occasions of their use, Mey (2001:p.54) declares that they are "pragmatically determined" since they "depend for their reference on the persons who use them". Leech and Short (1985: p.124) also affirm that deictics "vary systematically in their reference, according to the situation in which they are uttered". They derive their concrete meanings purely and squarely from the contextualization of their occurrence. And because we

necessarily replace personal/place names, objects and time we have mentioned earlier in a conversation with a substitute word (pronoun, adverb of place, adverb of place) to avoid the monotonous repetition of such words, the use of deictics cannot be avoided. According to Palmer, (1996:p.62) their occurrence in the daily use of language “cannot be ignored in the study of meaning, for ordinary language is full of their use”.

Since deictics are not interpretable in their own right but with reference to something else, in analyzing them we dwell on the concept of reference; we invariably analyze linguistic items that are tied to reference, that is, items which we can make meaning of only by making reference to something else. They are among the “... items in every language which have the property of reference...” and as such are not interpreted semantically (Halliday and Hasan, 1984:p.31). Furthermore, Halliday and Hasan (1984) explain that a hearer would have to refer to something else to give meaning to such linguistic items including “personals”, “demonstratives” and “comparatives”. The reference may be endophoric – retrievable from the linguistic context; or exophoric – retrievable from the non-linguistic context. Where reference is endophoric, it is either anaphoric – a backward one or cataphoric – a forward one.

This study draws data from the communication acts of characters in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s *Purple hibiscus*. The communication acts are randomly selected but with a view to reflecting the various types of deictic expressions, namely personal, temporal and spatial, that would often occur in conversations.

Contextualizing deictics in *Purple hibiscus*

There is a preponderance of deictic expressions in the conversations of characters of *Purple hibiscus* which is reflective of actual human communication. It is almost impracticable for the characters (people) here, as it is in reality, to use language without such expressions. The expressions occur at nearly every turn of their dialogues thereby making interlocutors to refer to their shared knowledge of context or the origin of such linguistic items for interpretation at alternate points in the process. Apart from conversations or interactions by the characters, narration by the protagonist-cum-narrator in the story also reflects the occurrence of the expressions as well as provides the necessary background for the dialogues and this facilitates the interpretation of the deictic items. Narration serves to establish the understanding between or among interlocutors in a given conversation situation. In addition, through the narration, a non-participant (or even the reader) becomes aware of the shared knowledge of the participants or the context of situation surrounding the usages. An otherwise indeterminate deictic expression is contextualized and assigned a referent due to an understanding.

The novel begins with a narration of the events of Palm Sunday. The second sentence of the opening paragraph bears a personal deictic item:

1. **We** had just returned from church (*Purple hibiscus*, 11).

The use of “**We**” in the expression above is contextualized in the opening sentence and so its meaning is recoverable from there: it refers to the narrator and members of her family to which there is an anaphoric reference. The decoder, (in this case the reader), ‘looks back’ to understand the referent of “**We**”. There is a continuous occurrence of such items in the narrative passage which gives the background to the events leading to the exchange between Papa and Jaja on Palm Sunday from where the reader is taken back in time with the section of the novel titled ‘Before Palm Sunday’.

An extract of the first set of communicative exchanges in the story which is between Papa and Jaja registers the occurrence of deictics:

2. “Jaja, **you** did not go to communion” Papa said quietly, almost a question.

“The wafer gives **me** bad breath”. “And the priest keeps touching my mouth and **it** nauseates **me**” Jaja said.

“**It** is the body of **our** Lord.” Papa’s voice was low, very low. “**You** cannot stop receiving the body of **our** Lord. **It** is death, **you** know **that**.” (pp. 14 – 15)

The items, “**you**”, “**me**”, “**it**”, “**our**”, “**that**” in the extract above are deictic items. Each of them has its meaning tied to this context of use. For example, the three instances of “**you**” refer here to Jaja but “**you**” can have another referent in another context because there is nothing that defines Jaja as “**you**” or anybody else to whom “**you**” can refer. “**It**” appears thrice above with different meanings in each case: In “...**it** nauseates me”, the action of the priest is referred to; in “**It** is the body ...” the communion (the wafer) is referred to; in “**It** is death, you know **that**”, the consequence believed to await non-communicants like Jaja wants to become is referred to. The meanings of all the deictic items used above are made definite only by this occasion of use without which their meanings would be indeterminate. As would be discovered with most such expressions, a backward (anaphoric) reference is made to know what the item stands for. Therefore, their meanings are not established in isolation or in a void but by the speaker’s and the hearer’s mutual understanding of its referent or by the physical context of use.

The constancy of occurrence of these expressions in the conversations by characters in this fictional world is reflective of their inevitability in the real world. We take more samples of such interactions for study. In this extract, the members of the Achike family are at their dining table:

3. “**They** brought **the cashew juice this** afternoon. **It** tastes good. **I** am sure **it** will sell,” Mama finally said.

“Ask **that** girl to bring **it**, Papa said.

Having called in Sisi, the housemaid, Mama says:

“Bring two bottles of the drink **they** brought from the factory.” (p. 20).

The pronouns and demonstratives which are given immediately above like all deictic expressions do not have definite referents but they are understood by the interlocutors in the context of the utterances in which they occur. The referent of “**they**” above is not found in the text; the speaker does not mention what or who “**they**” refers to. However, those involved in the exchange can deconstruct its referent from their non-linguistic experience – the factory workers known to this household are referred to. The referent of that item ‘**they**’ is exophoric; but it is inferred pragmatically by the interactants since (i) “**they**” refers to a group of people known to the interactants, (ii) the interactants are aware of what “**they**” do and where “**they**” come from, (iii) the interactants were expecting “**they**” to bring “**it**”, (iv) “**they**” brought “**it**” before the time of this exchange. Such an exophoric reference is made to an item not mentioned in the text and so it depends on the participants’ shared knowledge of context. Without that shared knowledge by the people engaged in the conversation, the meanings or referents of the exophora would be lost. But here as wherever it occurs, the people are able to recover the meanings from their understanding of the context. Halliday and Hasan (1984:pp.34 – 35) note that “exophoric reference is one form of context-dependence, since without context we cannot interpret what is said”.

The referent of “**it**” in both Mama’s and Papa’s utterances in the extract above is however endophoric because it is encoded in the utterance and it is the same thing– *the cashew juice*. Having been first mentioned before being replaced by the deictic item makes it an anaphora, a type of endophora. On the other hand, the demonstrative “**this**” in ‘this afternoon’ specifies the time of the action by “**they**” but its definitive meaning is tied to the immediate setting in which the statement is made. Taken away from there, “**this**” is no longer definitive but may describe any “**afternoon**”.

Papa’s response above equally has deictic items. Again, the demonstrative “**that**” in “**that** girl” is definitive or specified for the interactants only because they share the understanding of who is referred to: *the house girl, Sisi*. Of course also, “**that girl**” at another time with a new set of interactants in a new context will have a different referent. When Mama, following Papa’s instruction, tells “**that girl**”, “Bring two bottles of the drink **they** brought from the factory” (p. 20) “**they**” in Mama’s directive to Sisi is understood; ‘two bottles of the drink’ is also understood. Such reciprocal understanding enables conversationalists to reduce the tedium of having to repeat or to request every piece of information in an interaction. In the case above, without shared understanding, perhaps Sisi would have made any of the responses Kambili wished she made: “What bottles, Mama?” or “Where are they (the bottles), Madam?” (p. 20) or even “Who are they (the people)?”. Therefore, deictics or indexicals, as they are also called, have their meanings made out by interlocutors in the context of the speech outside of which they have no constant referents. Levinson (1983) suggests that interactants have “the ability to compute out of utterances in sequence the contextual assumptions they imply: the facts about the spatial, temporal and social relationship between participants, and their requisite beliefs and intentions in

undertaking certain verbal exchanges” (p. 49). That ability continually reflects whenever indexicals or deictic expressions occur.

In addition to different levels of knowledge shared by interlocutors, they make use of other non-linguistic behaviours such as gestures to facilitate the understanding of messages that contain deictics. When Papa says “**that girl**”, a gesture accompanies the utterance. Such gestures further define the referent of the deictic. According to Grundy (2008: p. 25) perhaps because deictics are semantically deficient, gestures often help their users to identify the referents. In the case above, Papa’s gesture identifies the referent.

More examples of instances of indexicals in *Purple hibiscus* are given below:

4. “Thank **you**, Mama, **I** was about to bring **them in**”, I said...

“A drizzle is coming. **I** did not want **them** to get wet” [Mama said] (p. 27)

For instance, in extract (4) above, we cannot interpret the meanings of “**I, them, in, I, them**” in isolation of the context or the users. Those linguistic items have their meanings tied to the characters uttering them and the place of uttering them. The pronoun “**I**” occurs twice in extract (4) but refers to different people at a time: Kambili and Mama. The adverb “**in**” can be understood only in terms of the location of the conversation, in this case, the Achikes’ house. “**Them**” is understood here by reference to the preceding narration where we can retrieve the information that Kambili and Jaja had washed and spread their uniforms outside to dry. The referents of **I, them, and in** would change in different contexts because the meanings of deictics are not exclusive (Mey, 2001; Lyons, 2002; Akmajian et al, 2001 etc). We find this in exclusivity when the same linguistic items occur in new contexts with different referents.

5. “Sister Beatrice, what is **it**? Why have you done **this**? Are **we** not content with the *anara* **we** are offered in other sisters’ homes?”(p. 29).

In (5) above, **it, you, this, we** are understood by the interactants in the context of that communication event: “**it**” refers to the action of providing a ‘little something’ by Sister Beatrice; “**you**” refers to Sister Beatrice; “**this**” also refers to the ‘little something’; and **we** refers to the members of Our Lady of the Miraculous Medal prayer group. It should be observed that the definite article “**the**” also has deictic function because it makes an item or a person identifiable in the situation as in “**the anara**” in the exchange in (5): it is not any *anara* but that identified by both the speaker and the hearer.

6. “Ade is easily the best out **there**,” Papa said... “Change of guard” what a headline. **They** are all afraid. Writing about how corrupt the civilian government was, as if **they** think the military will not be corrupt. **This** country is going down, way down.”

“God will deliver **us**,” I said...(pp. 33 – 34).

7. “**They** have taken **him!** **They** have taken **him!**” she said between throaty sobs.

“Yewande, Yewande”, Papa said, his voice much lower than hers. “What do I do,

Sir? I have three children!...”. (p. 45).

8. “**They** put out cigarettes on **his** back”. Papa said. “**They** put out so many cigarettes on **his** back”.

“**They** will receive their due, but not on this earth, *mba*”, Mama said.

“**We** are going to publish underground **now**”, Papa said. “**It** is no longer safe for my staff”.(p. 50)

“**They**” occurs in extracts (6), (7) and (8) above with different referents. The referent of each of “**they**” is not the same and is exophoric, not mentioned in the utterances. But the interlocutors understand who are referred to in each case: in (6), **they** stands for newspaper publishers; in (7), **they** stands for the agents of government; in (8), **they** stands for the torturers of Ade Coker. This again illustrates the inexpressiveness of the meanings of deictics, that they have different referents depending on context. It further illustrates the context-dependence of exophoric reference. Where a hearer does not connect to context, they would not understand the meaning of an instance of exophora.

Again, the referent of “**we**” in (5) is not the same as that of “**we**” in (8). Also, “**it**” in (5) and (8) do not have the same meaning due to the difference in context. The meaning of “**now**” in (8) depends on the time of utterance and the counteracting events. So, “**now**” can be defined or understood only in relation to the time of uttering it to the participants present.

Because “... ordinary language is full of the use of deictics” (Palmer, 1996: p. 62), the characters of this novel very often naturally use them as we can see in the extracts above. The meanings of those utterances depend crucially on the knowledge of the participants in the conversation and the circumstances of the utterances.

Deictic referents often occur anaphorically (behind the deictic item, after their antecedents have been given) as we have so far illustrated but there are times when they occur cataphorically where referents are to be found after the deictic item. That is, what is referred to by the deictic item comes after the item, its antecedent being in the forward position instead of the backward position as in: **It** was a facade, **the so-called election!** The deictic item “**It**” occurs here before its antecedent, ‘the so-called election’.

Here are more instances from the text under study:

9. “**That** child that helps me, Chinyelu, will come in soon. I will send her...” [Papa Nnukwu said] (p. 74)

10. “Because you’re bored with **it**? If only **we** all had satellite so everybody could be bored with **it**”.(p. 87)
11. “Look at **this**”, Papa Nnukwu said. “**This** is a woman spirit, and the women *mmuo* are harmless...”(p. 93)
12. “I discussed **it** with Father Benedict, and **he** says the children can go on pilgrimage to Aokpe...”(p. 115)
13. “Are you sure **they**’re not abnormal, mom? Kambili just behaved like an *atulu* when my friends came”.(p.150)
14. “**This** is about to bloom”, Aunty Ifeoma said to Jaja, pointing at an ixora bud. “Another two days and **it** will open **its** eyes to the world”.(p. 153)
15. “**I** see Christ in **their** faces, in **those** boys’ faces”.(p.185)

In (9), the referent for the demonstrative “**that**” is Chinyelu mentioned after it had been referred to by the deictic item. In (10), “**it**” has the referent “**satellite**” in the forward position in the utterance that follows. In (11), the referent for “**this**” is ‘*a woman spirit*’ also mentioned after the pronoun that refers to it. The referents for the pronouns in (12 – 15) are all in the forward position which we have referred to as cataphora. However, like all deictic expressions, cataphorically occurring items “refer to particular people or things, places and moments in time, respectively, but on different occasions they pick out different referents” (Spencer-Oatey and Zegerac, 2002: p.77). Items referred to in cataphora are traceable in the text and are therefore instances of endophora. The difference about them is simply that the deictic words occur before their referents even though they are contextualized within the utterance. All together, wherever they occur, the deictic items must be situated within some people-based, spatial or temporal context.

Conclusion

As deictic expressions are an integral part of ordinary language usage, they occur always in human communication as it shows in the conversation by the characters of Adichie’s *Purple hibiscus*. Even though we cannot cite all the instances of their occurrence here, it is self-evident that stretches of speech would hardly be made without the use of deictics and the need for contextualizing them. Their high occurrence in this fictional work signals or re-enacts their regular use in actual human speech and confirms the point that pragmatic phenomena occur often and are applied in human communication to aid understanding of messages and to reduce the tedium of having to say everything every time. Pragmatic knowledge and contextualization apply in verbal interactions so that we “don’t

have to spell out everything” every time we speak. This is so because even without everything being spelt out, interlocutors in a given communication are able to fill in the gaps with their understanding of the context of situation.

It is pertinent to also note that all the time deictic items occur, pragmatic inferences are to be made by the hearer for him/her to arrive at the meanings of such items. The inferences are normally made so intuitively and so easily that, like with other linguistic behaviours, the role of contextual knowledge that helps in the task is taken for granted. Pragmatic inferences are therefore a constant part of the interpretation of these items occurring in different utterances. By that, deictics establish the interconnection between the form of language and the contextual factors that influence its use.

References

- Adichie, C.N.(2006). *Purple Hibiscus*. Lagos: Farefina Books
- Akmajian, A., Demers, R. A., Farmer, A. K. & Harnish, R. M. (2001). *Linguistics: An introduction to language and communication*. New Delhi: Prentice-Hall.
- Austin, J. L. (1975). *How to do things with words*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Cohen, A, D. & Dornyei, Z. (2002). Focus on the language learner: Motivation, style and strategies. In N. Schmitt (ed.). *An introduction to applied linguistics*. London: Hodder Arnold.
- Fromkin, V. & Rodman, R. (1983). *An introduction to language*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Grundy, P. (2008). *Doing pragmatics*. London: Hodder Education.
- Halliday, M. A. K. & Hasan, R. (1984). *Cohesion in English*. London: Longman.
- Kress, G. & Hodge, R. (1993). *Language as ideology*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul
- Leckie-Tarry, H. (1995). *Language and context: A functional linguistic theory of register*. London: Pinter
- Leech, G. (1983). *Principles of pragmatics*. London: Longman
- Leech, G. N. & Short, M. H. (1985). *Style in fiction: A linguistic introduction to English fictional prose*. London: Longman.
- Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lyons, J. (2002). *Linguistic semantics: An introduction*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- McGregor, W. (2009). *Linguistics: An introduction*. London: Continuum International Publishing Group
- Mey, J. L. (2001). *Pragmatics: An introduction*. Malden: Blackwell.
- Palmer, F. R. (1996). *Semantics*. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Spencer-Oatey, H. & Zegezac, V. (2002). Pragmatics. In N. Schmitt (ed.). *An introduction to applied linguistics*. London: Hodder Arnold.
- Yule, G. (2003). *The study of language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.